

An Electron Spin Resonance Study of Fenton-Ruff Reagent*, Fe³⁺-H₂O₂ Solution System, using Ti⁴⁺ Ions as Free Radical Detector Ions

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Formation, decay and activation energy of free radical species in Fenton-Ruff reagent, Fe³⁺-H₂O₂ solutions were determined by electron spin resonance spectroscopy using Ti⁴⁺ ions as aqueous system free radical detector ions. At low modulation and low attenuation, a spectrum with two narrow lines, spaced a few gauss apart, with a width of 1G and g-values of 2.0128 and 2.0114 was generated. The relative signal intensities of the narrow spectra measured at 22°, after maximum values were reached, were dependent on the pH of the solutions, and the concentrations of hydrogen peroxide, Ti⁴⁺ ions, and Fe³⁺ ions. The overall decay of the chemical species responsible for esr spectra and thus the decomposition of hydrogen per-oxide was first order. The energy of activation of the reactions in Fe³⁺-H₂O₂ solutions was 10 ± 0.2 kcal/mole.

THE Fenton Reagent¹ and the Ruff reagent^{2,3} and their modified recipes have been discussed⁴⁻⁶. Haber and Willstätter⁷ and Haber and Weiss⁸ proposed the formation of perhydroxyl, HO₂[•] and hydroxyl, [•]OH free radicals in the reactions of Ruff reagents as follows :

In the presence of excess hydrogen peroxide, [•]OH radical reacts further :

This ensures higher concentration of HO₂[•] radicals in these solutions. [•]OH radical is very reactive, has a transient existence and is responsible for the reactions of this system with organic substrates. In the absence of substrates the overall result is a catalysed decomposition of hydrogen peroxide in which one molecule of hydrogen peroxide is oxidised and another is reduced.

The kinetics and mechanism of this decomposition of hydrogen peroxide has been a focus of many studies^{4,5,9-13}. The mechanisms proposed either envisage free radicals and ferrous ions as the primary (intermediate) products^{4,5,9,10} or tend to postulate active intermediates only and visualize free radicals as the reaction products of those active intermediates with the substrates¹¹⁻¹³.

The experimental evidence in support of the free radical hypothesis of Haber and Willstätter⁷, Haber and

Weiss⁸ has been provided by organic syntheses, polymerization and graft-polymerization reactions of vinyl monomers, by observance of esr spectra of the free radicals generated by these and similar systems on various organic substances. Kremer¹¹ and Kremer and Stein¹² have suggested that if free radicals are formed in this system, they are limited to reactions which are kinetically insignificant. Jones and Perkins¹³ suggested two electron equivalent atom-transfer processes in this system. Garten¹⁷ suggested that both free radical and non-free radical mechanisms occur in the system.

Bains *et. al.* reported the use of Ti⁴⁺ ions as esr detector ions in the systems²⁰, Fe³⁺-H₂O₂, and Ce⁴⁺-H₂O₂, the free radicals of which systems are not detectable without the presence of Ti⁴⁺ and some other ions such as Zr⁴⁺, Hf⁴⁺, Th⁴⁺, UO₂²⁺ and VO₂⁺ ions using flow systems^{21,22}. Czapski *et. al.*,²³⁻²⁵ Ingold²⁶, Seteka *et. al.*,²⁷ Shimizu *et. al.*,²⁸ and Tkáč *et. al.*^{29,30} have also reported esr evidence for the formation of complexes with radicals in flow systems that contain "Fentonlike" reagents and peroxy radicals. Through a study of formation, decay and activation energy of free radical species, we are communicating esr evidence in support of the formation of free radicals in the Fe³⁺-H₂O₂ system. A discussion as to the nature of the chemical species will be given.

Experimental

A Varian 4502-15 epr spectrometer, operated at 100-kc field modulation and equipped with an aqueous cell, was used. The epr spectrometer was also equipped with a variable temperature accessory. The temperature of solution in the aqueous cell was regulated at 0° to 45° during recording of the esr spectra and estimating of the concentrations of the active radical species. Solutions that had the compositions indicated

*Barring the fast initial oxidation of Fe³⁺ ions by hydrogen peroxide in the Fenton reagent, Fe³⁺-H₂O₂, it is similar to Ruff reagent, Fe²⁺-H₂O₂. Hence the name Fenton-Ruff reagent for this system is being used.

in the captions to Figures 1-5, at the desired temperatures, were mixed rapidly and placed in the resonant cavity of the spectrometer. The concentrations of active radical species reached maximum values within 60 sec. These values were relatively stable, until the reactants that were initially present in large excesses, as compared with the concentrations of the radical species, were depleted. Ti^{4+} ions were added to Fe^{3+} - H_2O_2 solutions to yield complexes with radical species formed that were esr detectable^{20,22}. On mixing solutions of Ti^{4+} ions and H_2O_2 or of Fe^{3+} ions and H_2O_2 , no esr spectra were generated.

Results

When solutions of Fe^{3+} ions and H_2O_2 , containing Ti^{4+} ions, are mixed in an aqueous sample cell in the cavity of the epr spectrometer, the spectrum, generated under equilibrium conditions at 22°, is shown in Figure 1. Recorded at low modulation amplitude (80 units) and low attenuation, two narrow lines, spaced a few gauss

Figure 1. ESR spectrum generated under stationary state conditions in Fe^{3+} - H_2O_2 solution containing Ti^{4+} ions. $FeNH_4(SO_4)_2$ 0.0025M, H_2O_2 0.05M, $TiCl_4$ 0.05M, pH 1.5. Recorded at low modulation amplitude, low attenuation, and 100-kc field modulation. Magnetic field increasing left to right.

apart, with a width of about 1G and g-values of 2.0128 and 2.0114 were observed. Recorded at high modulation amplitude (800 units) and low attenuation, only a singlet spectrum with a line width of about 2G was observed. If Ti^{4+} ions were omitted from the solution, no esr spectrum was generated. The esr spectrum generated by the Fe^{3+} - H_2O_2 system was similar to those recorded for the Ti^{3+} - H_2O_2 system³¹⁻³⁵ and Fe^{3+} - H_2O_2 system^{20,22}. The relative intensities of the narrow spectra, measured at 22° after maximum

values were reached, were dependent on the pH of the solutions and the concentrations of Fe^{3+} ions, H_2O_2 and Ti^{4+} ions, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Relative intensities of esr spectra generated by the Fe^{3+} - H_2O_2 solution containing Ti^{4+} ions at 22°: (Δ) $FeNH_4(SO_4)_2$ 0.001M, H_2O_2 0.2M, $TiCl_4$ 0.05M; (\triangle) $FeNH_4(SO_4)_2$ 0.005M, H_2O_2 0.5M, $TiCl_4$ 0.01M; (O) $FeNH_4(SO_4)_2$ 0.0025M, H_2O_2 0.05M, $TiCl_4$ 0.01M. Recorded at high modulation amplitude.

The relative intensities of the spectra, within the narrow pH range of 0.8-1.9, where this study is feasible increased with increase in pH of the solution as shown in Fig. 2-A. The same data plotted as signal versus reciprocal of hydrogen ion concentration gives reasonably straight plots as shown in Fig. 2-B. That signal intensity is lowered with increasing hydrogen ion concentration and vice versa in this solution system has a bearing on reaction 1 and the behaviour of catalase in the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide; higher pH favours production of free radicals.

Figure 3. Dependence of signal intensity on the concentration of hydrogen peroxide, Ti^{4+} ions and Fe^{3+} ions respectively at pH 1.5 and 2.0.
 (A) $TiCl_4$ 0.01M, $FeNH_4(SO_4)$ 0.01M ;
 (B) $FeNH_4(SO_4)_2$ 0.01M, H_2O_2 0.01M ;
 (C) $TiCl_4$ 0.01M, H_2O_2 0.01M.

The dependence of signal intensity on concentration of hydrogen peroxide at pH 1.5 and 2.0 is indicated by two parallel plots in Fig. 3-A. This shows that either the rate of free radical production is enhanced by a decrease in hydrogen ion concentration and/or the nature of Ti^{4+} complexes with hydrogen peroxide changes so as to make them act as better free radical detector species. However it is wellknown that with increasing pH, the rate of decomposition of hydrogen peroxide increases.

In Fig. 3-B is a plot showing that signal intensity increased with $[Ti^{4+}]$. This behavior is the same as that shown in the $Ce^{4+}-H_2O_2$ and $Fe^{3+}-H_2O_2$ systems²⁰.

An increase in the concentration of Fe^{3+} ion did not have a marked effect on signal intensity as indicated in Fig. 3-C. At higher pH signal intensity increased with concentration of Fe^{3+} ion up to 0.005M and dropped with further increase. At high concentration, Fe^{3+} ion may scavenge the HO_2 radicals as follows :

As will be indicated below, the rate of decomposition of hydrogen peroxide and thus the rate of production of free radicals is proportional to the concentration of Fe^{3+} ion. It suggests that free radical producing reaction (1) is, as required by the proposed Haber and Weiss mechanism, a bimolecular reaction with rate proportional to both $[H_2O_2]$ and $[Fe^{3+}]$. The signal intensity at constant $[Ti^{4+}]$ and $[H^+]$ is solely determined by this reaction. Furthermore decrease in signal intensity with lowering in free radical concentration as a result of reaction (5) indicates that Ti^{4+} ion is acting as an indicator ion.

The disappearance of esr spectrum generated in these systems is shown in Figure 4. When temperature of the solutions was raised, the rate of disappearance of esr signal increased. The rate of disappearance at 25° was much lower than at about 43°. At pH 1.7 and 43° the rate of disappearance is first order, with a half life of 4.5 min. This indicates that hydrogen peroxide is decomposed in a pseudo first order decay rate. The signal disappearance experiments indicated that decomposition of hydrogen peroxide is directly proportional to the concentration of Fe^{3+} ion.

Figure 4. Effects of temperature and pH on rate of free radical decay in Fe³⁺-H₂O₂ solution containing Ti⁴⁺ ions: solution composition -FeNH₄(SO₄)₂ 0.01M, H₂O₂ 0.02M, TiCl₄ 0.1M; (O) prepared at 25° and pH 1.7, held for 90 sec then temperature increased to 43° and decay measured; (Δ) prepared at 41° and pH 1.9 and decay measured immediately; (□) prepared at 43° and pH 1.7 and decay measured immediately. Recorded at high modulation amplitude; (×) prepared at 25° and decay measured immediately.

Fig. 4B

The decay of the free radical species probably resulted from unimolecular reactions. Lindemann^{36,37} suggested that the behavior of unimolecular reactions can be explained on the basis of bimolecular collisions provided that a time lag exists between activation and reaction during which activated molecules may either react or be deactivated to ordinary molecules. There-

fore, the rate of reaction will be proportional only to those molecules that remain active, as follows:

Where $k_2 [R] [R^*] \gg k_3 [R^*]$, we obtain

$$-\frac{d[R]}{dt} = k[R^*]$$

that is, the rate of reaction of R to form products is proportional to the concentration of free radicals. Assuming that the concentration of free radicals is proportional to the relative intensity of the singlet esr spectrum measured at high modulation amplitude, the energy of activation for radical reactions in Fe³⁺-H₂O₂ solutions was calculated from the Arrhenius plot, shown in Figure 5, to be 10 ± 0.2 kcal/mole.

The energy of activation for radical reactions in Fe³⁺-H₂O₂ solutions was relatively constant over the pH range 1.3-1.9.

Figure 5. Arrhenius plot of energy of activation for radical reactions in Fe^{3+} - H_2O_2 solution containing Ti^{4+} ions: solution composition -- $\text{FeNH}_4(\text{SO}_4)_2$, $0.01M$, H_2O_2 , $0.02M$, TiCl_4 , $0.01M$; (A) pH 1.3; (B) pH 1.7; (C) pH 1.9.

Discussion

Because of dielectric loss of the medium, nature of spin orbit coupling in OH and HO_2 radicals and the atomic, molecular and radical exchange phenomenon characteristic of aqueous solutions, esr spectra were not detected except in frozen solutions. The practical difficulty of freezing the radicals after their production in redox solution systems is obvious and formidable. The development of Ti^{4+} ions²⁰ and other metal ions^{21,22} such as Zr^{4+} , Hf^{4+} , Th^{4+} , UO_2^{2+} and VO_2^+ as free radical detector species has obviated the difficulty.

The use of Ti^{4+} ions as an essential component detecting the free radicals through an esr signal in the Fe^{3+} - H_2O_2 solution system has made a direct study of the Fenton-Ruff Reagent feasible. It seems that free radical mechanism proposed by Haber and Weiss^{7,8} is the most significant one.

Since Ti^{4+} ions do not participate in oxidation-reduction reactions the only role of these ions is, through complex formation, that of acting as the "detector" ions for the free radicals. That the signal is proportional to the concentration of Ti^{4+} ions shows that free radicals associated with or bound to these ions are only a small fraction of the free radicals which are free and unbound in the solution⁹. This ensures that the addition of further quantities of Ti^{4+} does not affect the concentration of free radicals in solution giving the proportionality behaviour; additional Ti^{4+} ions take up only a small fraction of the total free radical concentration.

In the narrow pH range of 0.8-1.9, other metal ions that acted as indicator ions are UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} and their behaviour was similar to that of the Ti^{4+} indicator ions. This indicated that only sufficiently basic metallic species would give esr spectra; Zr^{4+} and Hf^{4+} species may form polynuclear species making smaller number of sites available for interaction with free radicals. At a low pH where the metal ion species would be in a suitable solution state to give esr spectra-producing species, the concentration of free radicals formed is low on account of a slow reaction.

The free radicals formed in Fe^{3+} - H_2O_2 solution are evidently exchanged with ligands of metal ions with specific characteristics to form radical complex species during which process the spin orbit coupling is undone and the radicals are detected under normal conditions. For detection purposes the metal ions should have no d-electrons; and the d-orbitals should be vacant for ligand coordination and exchange so that free radicals in the complexed and free state are in equilibrium.

Medalia and Kolthoff²³ suggested that ferryl ion, FeO^{2+} proposed by Bray and Gorin¹⁹ for this system could react with the substrate to yield free radicals without involving free radicals or free radical intermediates in the parent Fenton-Ruff reagent. This would suggest that reaction of FeO^{2+} ion with inorganic substrates such as phosphoric acid, H_3PO_4 , aluminum ions, Al^{3+} (aq), boric acid, H_3BO_3 etc. would yield free radicals; on addition of H_3PO_4 , Al^{3+} (aq), boric acid, etc. to the Fe^{3+} - H_2O_2 solution no esr spectrum was generated.

Jones and Perkins' theoretical position¹⁹ also does not seem tenable at least for the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide by ferric ions and we hope that the use of Ti^{4+} and other esr detector ions may also elucidate the catalase reactions.

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